

Why russian children struggle with English: an evaluation of the Spotlight coursebook set based on Miekley's checklist

Introduction

This paper critically evaluates the English language textbook *Spotlight 2*, widely used in Russian primary schools as the entry point for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction. Drawing on Joshua Miekley's (2005) EFL Textbook Evaluation Checklist, this study examines the textbook's content, methodology, and practical implementation, highlighting challenges it poses for young learners who begin without prior phonetic training or basic vocabulary.

This study analyses English textbooks for teaching English as a foreign language (EFL) in Russian schools. A significant problem has been identified whereby many students encounter difficulties at the very beginning stage of learning English. Typically, instruction begins in the second grade using the *Spotlight 2* textbook, while the introductory Starter course is frequently omitted. Consequently, learners study English without foundational sound-letter correspondence training, phonetic skills, or basic vocabulary. This results in a high cognitive load that negatively affects students' motivation and confidence. At this stage, students are generally 7–8 years old. The analysis focuses on the *Spotlight* series, the most commonly used EFL textbook complex in Russian primary education. The evaluation was conducted using the ESL/EFL textbook evaluation checklist developed by Joshua Miekley (2005). The completed checklist is provided in Appendix A.

Course materials overview

The Spotlight educational and methodical complex was developed in cooperation between Russian and British publishing houses: “Prosveshchenie” and Express Publishing. It is included in the Federal List of textbooks approved by the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation for use in general educational institutions. The complex is intended to teach English as a foreign language in three academic hours per week, with each lesson lasting 45 minutes. The composition of the Spotlight textbook includes a student's Book, Workbook, Teacher's Book, Audio CD, and Test Booklet. The complex is based on the communicative-cognitive approach.

This essay evaluated the Spotlight 2 textbook (Student's Book for the second grade), the starting point for English language learning in most Russian schools. The Spotlight 2 textbook is used in the second grade of Russian comprehensive schools as a starter English language learning course. The complex includes an introductory course, Spotlight Starter, for Grade 1. However, in most Russian schools (up to 95%), this level is not used and is omitted since in the first grade, English is not a compulsory part of the curriculum and is often replaced by other subjects. (Rossiyskaya Gazeta, 2021). The student book Spotlight 2 consists of two parts.

The student book Spotlight 2 received 8 out of a possible 16 points in the Content section of the Joshua Miekley Textbook Evaluation Checklist. The content of the Spotlight 2 textbook is logically organised: it is presented in the form of thematic modules (“My Home”, “My Birthday”, “My Animals”, etc.), each of which includes vocabulary, grammar, and practical tasks. The quality of the reading texts was a weakness: they are not authentic enough, poorly reflect real speech situations, and

practically do not give students an idea of a living language (see Figure 1). In addition, the cultural component is only superficially revealed, and literary genres and syntactic variety are presented in a limited way: songs, poems and dialogues. The criterion of having topics that stimulate critical thinking does not apply to this age of students and, therefore, was not evaluated. In the textbook, all instructions and explanations are given in L1.

Contents

Part 1

Let's Go!	p. 4
My Letters!	p. 6
Starter Module Hello! My Family!	p. 18
Module 1 My Home!	p. 26
Module 2 My Birthday!	p. 44
Activities	p. 62
Spotlight on Russia	p. 64
My Letters! – Phonetics	p. 65
First Steps to Reading	p. 66
Word List	p. 71

 – задание рекомендуется выполнять в личной тетради учащегося

Сканируй, открывай и слушай!

<https://prosv.ru/audio-spotlight2-1/>

Let's Go!

1 Спой песенку.

Hello, hello, everyone,
I'm Nanny Shine, hello!
Come in and get ready,
Come on, everyone –
let's go!

My name is Nanny Shine.
Tell me what's your name.
My name is Nanny Shine.
Nanny Shine's my name!

2 Поговори со своим одноклассником, используя образец.

Hello, I'm Nanny Shine. What's your name?

Hello, I'm Anna.

Figure 1

Table of contents and page 4 from the Spotlight 2 Student's Book, part 1.

Note. Reprinted from potlight 2: Student's Book. Part 1, by N. I. Bykova, D. Dooley, M. D. Pospelova, & V. Evans, 2022, Prosveshchenie. Copyright 2022 by Prosveshchenie.

In the “Vocabulary and Grammar” section, the Spotlight 2 textbook scored 7 out of 20 possible points, indicating a low implementation level of this component. The pace of the material is excessively high: letters and sounds are studied in just four lessons, strictly in alphabetical order (it gives 8 letters per lesson), after which pupils go straight to reading words and phrases without mastering basic phonetic skills. Below is an exercise from page 11, which children who have just started learning the language in this textbook should do as early as the 6th language lesson. It suggests reading words containing doubled consonants, consonant blends, diphthongs, triphthongs, magic e, etc. (see Figure 2). Children who have just been introduced to the sounds and letters of a new language cannot read these on their own, only by memorising whole words.

My Letters!

1 Слушай и повторяй за диктором.

r rabbit

s snake

t tree

u umbrella

v vest

w window

x box

y yacht

z zip

2 Спой песенку.

3 Перепиши слова в тетрадь, вставляя пропущенные буквы.

1 w _ _ d _ w

3 _ m _ _ e _ la

5 _ _ p

7 t _ _ e

9 _ _ b _ _ t

2 _ e _ t

4 b _ x

6 s _ _ k _

8 _ a _ h _

4 Прочитай слова и выбери правильный ответ.

1 a horse b snake c kangaroo

2 a box b yacht c jug

3 a mouse b dog c rabbit

4 a glass b vest c nest

Figure 2

Pages 10-11 from the Spotlight 2 Student's Book, part 1.

Note. Same source as Figure 1.

New vocabulary is introduced quickly and piecemeal, often in word lists (e.g., animals, colours, kitchen supplies together in one list) rather than through coherent dialogues or context. And the exercise on the textbook page is not related to vocabulary (see Figure 3). Grammatical constructions are given in parallel with new vocabulary. Repetition of the studied material occurs, but irregularly.

2

cat
lamp
horse
pin
jug
rabbit
orange
window

1

cat
CAT

5

3 Спой песенку, сопровождая её движениями.

A B C D E F G H I J K L M,
I can sing the alphabet,
Can you do the same?
I can sing the alphabet,
I've got it in my head!
N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z!

17

Figure 3

Page 17 from the Spotlight 2 Student's Book, part 1.

Note. Same source as Figure 1.

The Spotlight 2 textbook scored 15 out of 24 points in the “Exercises and tasks” section, corresponding to an above-average level. The strength is the presence of

interactive tasks that encourage students to use new vocabulary in context (e.g., composing dialogues, mini-scenes, descriptions). Clear and understandable instructions accompany the tasks. All tasks are written in L1.

The most significant disadvantage of the Spotlight 2 textbook is the lack of systematic work on teaching reading. As a result, children do not understand the principles of reading, memorise words in their entirety, and do not know how to “parse” them into sounds and letters. This hampers the formation of the skill of conscious reading and further hinders the expansion of vocabulary and the development of written speech. Reading strategies are used only sparingly and without systematic instruction. Pupils are offered a preliminary content prediction from an illustration, but keyword work is not offered.

For example, on page 31 (Module 1, Lesson 2a), children first look at the picture and answer “Where is Chuckles?” in their native language. They describe the picture and guess. However, the main character, the monkey Chuckles (a very difficult name for children who have just started learning the language), is not in the illustration, i.e. it is impossible to guess and predict. And only from the text can you understand that he is in the house. Then, they listen to the song to check the answer. Children do not learn to read the words — they listen and remember (see Figure 4).

3 Посмотри на картинку. Как ты думаешь, где сейчас Чаклз? Прслушай песенку и узнай правильный ответ.

2a

Where's Chuckles?
He's in the house!
Oh no! He's in the house!

Where's Mummy?
She's in the kitchen!
Where's Daddy?
He's in the bedroom!

Chuckles, come here!
Chuckles, come here!
Chuckles is in the house!

4 Прочитай текст песенки и выбери правильный ответ.

1 Mummy is ... a in the bedroom.
2 Daddy is ... b in the kitchen.

Module 1 31

Figure 4 Page 31 from the *Spotlight 2 Student's Book, part 1*.

Note. Same source as Figure 1.

The introduction of new lexico-grammatical units is often often simultaneous. The textbook does not explain the apostrophe symbol and its meaning but is used on the book's first page. Consider the task from the first module of the textbook, p. 29, after the beginning of a new language (see Figure 5). The vocabulary furniture is introduced simultaneously, and several grammatical constructions are introduced (ex.1), each including affirmative, negative and interrogative sentences (see Figure 5). Children are asked to look at an illustration and ask a question. Give an affirmative or negative answer, or immediately name the object.

1b

1 Посмотри на картинку и задай вопрос однокласснику по образцу.

- Is it a chair?
- Yes, it is./No, it isn't. It's a table.

2 Представь, что это комната Лулу, и скажи, что в ней есть.

She's got a white bed.

Как ты думаешь, что есть в комнате у Ларри? Скажи.

He's got a ...

28 Module 1

Figure 5

Page 28 from the *Spotlight 2 Student's Book, part 1*.

Note. Same source as Figure 1.

In the same lesson, children are asked to practice another "we have" construction, using different pronouns and shortened forms. We've instead of we have (see Figure 6). The textbook offers insufficient attention and time for memorising pronouns and understanding the construction itself. Students memorise the phrase by repetition.

4 Что скажут Ларри и Лулу о своём домике?
We've got a
А что скажет мама об их домике?
They've got a

Module 1 29

Figure 6

Page 29 from the Spotlight 2 Student's Book, part 1.

Note. Same source as Figure 1.

The last criterion evaluated was the attractiveness of the text and design. The textbook received high scores for visual design: bright, detailed illustrations are well integrated into the text and contribute to understanding the text. The topics and pictures are age-appropriate for the students and motivate learning. However, there is a visual blending of L1 and L2 languages. The illustrations take up much space, and the Russian and English text are placed close together. There is no emphasis on what is being practised and learned.

The Spotlight 2 textbook scored about 60% of the maximum possible score on the Mickley checklist criteria.

Balance of coursebook, supplementary and authentic materials

The Spotlight 2 curriculum includes additional materials: Workbook, Test Booklet, audio CD, and teacher's materials. The course demonstrates a reasonable balance between coursebook materials, supplementary practice, and authentic resources. However, there are some problems. Their presence, unfortunately, does not fully

compensate for the methodological limitations of the main textbook, such as the high density of the material, the accelerated study of the alphabet, lack of reading skills, isolated work on grammatical constructions and lexical units, and a weak system of repetition.

Many exercises for assessing the degree of learning English vocabulary on a certain topic are contained in the Workbook. Still, most secondary schools and teachers do not ask parents to buy workbooks for schoolchildren, and schools themselves do not, so the Workbook for schoolchildren is also rarely used for practising skills.

Knowledge control book materials (tests) are also rarely used in schools. This is because not all teachers have this collection of control tasks or deliberately avoid using it due to the availability of ready-made answers on the Internet, which makes knowledge testing ineffective. Teachers are often forced to look for exercises, lexical games, and additional tasks from external resources, including pedagogical communities, blogs, and methodological groups. However, with restricted access to YouTube and other platforms where quality authentic materials were previously available, using original videos, songs, and cartoons has become difficult. In lessons, only the audio CD that comes with the textbook is often used, severely limiting listening and cultural context.

The teacher's guide is written in Russian and includes examples of words and phrases that the teacher is expected to say in English during each lesson. The guide was evaluated using the Joshua Miekley checklist. In the "General Characteristics" section, the book scored 8 out of 8 points. However, it lacks a reference section. The "Content and Curriculum Fit" section received 21 out of 28 points. The guide does not significantly expand the teacher's knowledge or provide alternative teaching methods.

Lessons are presented in a basic format and follow the main steps of a standard lesson (see Figure 7). Overall, the teacher's guide can be considered satisfactory. See translation in Appendix B.

MY LETTERS!

В английском языке многие названия букв не соответствуют звукам, которые они передают. Многие правила чтения также представляют большую сложность для учащихся раннего возраста, т.к. многие слова, с которыми они знакомятся на начальном этапе, читаются не по правилам. Это нередко вызывает у детей чувство растерянности и неудовлетворенности. Поэтому в данном УМК дети, изучая алфавит, знакомятся сначала со звуками, а потом с названиями букв. Это происходит в такой последовательности: звук, который передает буква, и слово с соответствующим звуком произносятся учителем, и дети видят картинку, иллюстрирующую это слово. Они повторяют звук и слово за учителем, потом за диктором и смотрят на картинку и на слово в учебнике. Таким образом они учатся соотносить звуковой и графический образ слова и затем без труда узнают это слово в контексте. Когда дети будут знакомиться с названиями букв (с.17 упр.3), не нужно настаивать на том, чтобы они сразу выучили весь алфавит. У них будет возможность сделать это в течение года.

Урок а (с. 6–7)

Задача урока: познакомить учащихся с буквами английского алфавита (*a–h*) в правильной последовательности, формировать умение фонетически корректно их озвучивать и графически корректно воспроизводить.

Лексика для чтения: *ant, bed, cat, dog, egg, flag, glass, horse.*

Актуализация лексики/структур: *Hello! I'm My name is What's your name? How are you? Fine, thanks. Goodbye!*

Речь учителя на уроке: *Open your books at page ... ! Listen, point and repeat! Look and write! What's this? Well done, one point, two points!*

Оснащение урока: картинки *My Letters!*

➤ **Начало урока**

1. Учитель и учащиеся приветствуют друг друга. Учитель спрашивает детей: *How are you?*

Дети отвечают: *Fine, thanks.*

2. Учитель вызывает двух учащихся к доске и просит их представиться друг другу. Сначала учитель напоминает, как это делать. Например:

Вероника: *Hello, I'm Veronika.*

What's your name?

Миша: *Hello, I'm Misha.*

И т. д.

➤ **Введение алфавита**

3. Учитель пишет на доске или показывает на карточке строчную букву *a*. Показывая на букву *a*, он произносит */æ/*. Учащиеся повторяют звук хором и индивидуально. Учитель показывает картинку с изображением муравья и говорит: */æ/ — /ænt/*. Затем учитель рядом с буквой *a* пишет слово/прикрепляет карточку со словом *ant*, показывает на букву и слово и говорит: */æ/ — /ænt/*. Учащиеся повторяют хором и индивидуально. Учитель показывает на букву, картинку, слово и говорит: */æ/ — /ænt/ — /ænt/*. После этого учитель пишет на доске букву *a* еще раз, показывая движением руки её написание. Учащиеся пишут 1–2 буквы *a* в Рабочей тетради (с. 4, упр. 1). Аналогично вводятся остальные буквы и слова.

33

4. Учитель пишет на доске крупно номер страницы «6» и говорит: *Open your books at page six.*

5. **С. 6, упр. 1.** Учитель с помощью мимики и жестов объясняет задание и говорит: *Listen, point and repeat!* Учащиеся слушают запись и в паузах повторяют звуки и слова хором и индивидуально. Когда запись звучит еще раз, учитель показывает на доске на картинку букв и слов и на картинку, иллюстрирующие слова, а дети произносят буквы и слова, показывая их в учебниках. При необходимости прослушивание повторяется.

6. **С. 6, упр. 2.** Дети слушают рифмовку в записи и следят по картинкам, показывая на буквы и слова. Во время последующих прослушиваний дети начинают постепенно повторять то, что они запомнили. Запись прослушивается столько раз, сколько учитель сочтет необходимым. Учитель показывает на буквы и слова, а дети повторяют рифмовку самостоятельно.

7. **С. 7, упр. 3.** Учитель просит детей посмотреть на картинки и спрашивает: *What's this?* Дети отвечают: *horse, cat* и т. д. Затем учитель объясняет задание и дает детям достаточно времени для того, чтобы они написали первую букву слова в своих тетрадях. Для проверки ответов дети по очереди называют звук и слово.

1. */h/ — horse* 3. */æ/ — ant* 5. */g/ — glass* 7. */d/ — dog*
2. */t/ — cat* 4. */e/ — egg* 6. */f/ — flag* 8. */b/ — bed*

➤ **Конец урока**

8. Класс делится на две команды *A* и *B*. Учитель на доске рисует две колонки и подписывает одну *A*, другую *B*. Затем он показывает на одну из написанных на доске букв и просит ученика из команды *A* озвучить букву/назвать слово, начинающееся с этого звука, или сделать и то, и другое. Если ученик правильно назвал звук, он получает одно очко. Если ученик назвал слово, начинающееся с этого звука, он также получает одно очко. Если ученик назвал правильно и звук, и слово, он получает два очка. Затем учитель обращается к команде *B*. Побеждает команда, набравшая больше очков. Например:

Учитель показывает на букву b.

Команда A:

Ученик 1: */b/*

Учитель: *1 point.*

Учитель показывает на букву d.

Команда B:

Ученик 1: *dog*

Учитель: *1 point.*

Учитель показывает на букву g.

Команда A:

Ученик 2: */g/ — glass*

Учитель: *Well done! 2 points.*

9. Заканчивая урок, учитель говорит: *Goodbye, children!* Дети отвечают: *Goodbye (Мария Александровна)!*

Рабочая тетрадь

В классе или дома выполняются упражнения из Рабочей тетради (с. 4, упр. 1, 2). Прежде чем задать упражнения на дом, учитель объясняет, как их выполнять. Дополнительные рекомендации по работе с ними можно найти на с. 142.

Примечание. Для дальнейшей отработки написания букв учащимся рекомендуется

34

Figure 7

Pages 33-34 from the Spotlight 2 Teacher's Book

Note. Reprinted from potlight 2: Teacher's Book. by N. I. Bykova, 2022,

Prosveshchenie. Copyright 2022 by Prosveshchenie.

Gaps in materials and potential sources

The materials that are most lacking are those aimed at systematic reading instruction: letter-sound parsing tasks, CVC syllable exercises, practising reading with the “magic e”, and other basic models of English phonetics. Missing resources can be found on the British Council - LearnEnglish Kids, Twinkl, and teacher blogs. Also, there are not enough extra materials to practice vocabulary. Teachers can use flashcards and word cards or make mind maps to help students remember words better. There are also not enough materials to practice grammar rules step by step. Teachers can create such materials using AI tools or find ready-made worksheets on websites like Teachers Pay Teachers (TPT) (see Figure 8).

In general, despite its colourful design, logical structure and additional materials, the Spotlight 2 textbook is poorly suited for the beginning of learning English as a foreign language. It does not provide the necessary step-by-step preparation for reading, does not provide a sufficient phonetic base, and does not offer a methodologically structured entry into the language. It can explain why students in Russian schools face overload and misunderstanding and often lose motivation for the subject at the very early stages.

References

- AbdelWahab, M. M. (2013). Developing an English language textbook evaluative checklist. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 1(3), 55–70.
- Bykova, N. I., Dooley, D., Pospelova, M. D., & Evans, V. (2022). *Spotlight 2: Student's Book. Part 1*. Prosveshchenie.
- Bykova, N. I., et al. (2022). *Spotlight 2: Teacher's Book*. Prosveshchenie.
- Miekley, J. (2005). ESL/EFL textbook evaluation checklist. *The Reading Matrix*, 5(2), 1–14.
- Shieh, J.-J., Reynolds, B. L., & Ha, X. V. (2023). Using a design-based approach to develop a checklist for evaluating preservice teacher learning materials. *TESOL Journal*, 14(3), Article e717.

Appendix A

Completed EFL Textbook Evaluation Checklist (Spotlight 2, Part 1) based on Miekley (2005)

Textbook Evaluation Checklist		Excellent	Good	Adequate	Poor	Totally Lacking	Mandatory	Optional	Not Applicable
I. Textbook									
A. Content									
i. Is the subject matter presented either topically or functionally in a logical, organized manner? (1,2,3) ^a		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
ii. Does the content serve as a window into learning about the target language culture (American, British, ect.)? (2,18)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
iii. Are the reading selections authentic pieces of language? (5,10)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
iv. Compared to texts for native speakers, does the content contain real-life issues that challenge the reader to think critically about his/her worldview? (1,2,3,7,21)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
v. Are the text selections representative of the variety of literary genres, and do they contain multiple sentence structures? (1,13)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
B. Vocabulary and Grammar									
i. Are the grammar rules presented in a logical manner and in increasing order of difficulty? (1,2,3)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
ii. Are the new vocabulary words presented in a variety of ways (e.g. glosses, multi-glosses, appositives)? (2,3,12)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
iii. Are the new vocabulary words presented at an appropriate rate so that the text is understandable and so that students are able to retain new vocabulary? (1,2,3,5)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
iv. Are the new vocabulary words repeated in subsequent lessons to reinforce their meaning and use? (1,2,3)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
v. Are students taught top-down techniques for learning new vocabulary words? (7,8,9,11)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
C. Exercises and Activities									
i. Are there interactive and task-based activities that require students to use new vocabulary to communicate? (1,2,3,5)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
ii. Do instructions in the textbook tell students to read for comprehension? (6)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
iii. Are top-down and bottom-up reading strategies used? (17)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
iv. Are students given sufficient examples to learn top-down techniques for reading comprehension? (7,8,9,10)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
v. Do the activities facilitate students' use of grammar rules by creating situations in which these rules are needed? (1,2,3)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
vi. Does the text make comprehension easier by addressing one new concept at a time instead of multiple new concepts? (2,3)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
vii. Do the exercises promote critical thinking of the text? (2)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
D. Attractiveness of the Text and Physical Make-up									
i. Is the cover of the book appealing? (1,2,3)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
ii. Is the visual imagery of high aesthetic quality? (1,2,3,14)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
iii. Are the illustrations simple enough and close enough to the text that they add to its meaning rather than detracting from it? (1)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N
iv. Is the text interesting enough that students will enjoy reading it? (15)		4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N

46 / 76
60,5 %

Completed EFL Teacher's Manual Evaluation Checklist based on Miekley (2005)

II Teacher's Manual									
A. General Features									
i. Does the manual help teachers understand the objectives and methodology of the text? (1,2,3)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
ii. Are correct or suggested answers given for the exercises in the textbook? (1,2,3,4)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
B. Background Information									
i. Are teachers shown how to teach students to use cues from morphology, cognates, rhetorical relationships, and context to assist them in lexical inferencing? (7)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
ii. Is there a list of true and false cognates for vocabulary words? (1,2,3)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
C. Methodological Guidance									
i. Are teachers given techniques for activating students' background knowledge before reading the text? (8,9,22)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
ii. Are teachers given adequate examples for teaching students to preview, skim, scan, summarize, and to find the main idea? (8,11,6)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
iii. Does the manual suggest a clear, concise method for teaching each lesson? (1,2,3)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
D. Supplementary Exercises and Materials									
i. Does the manual give instructions on how to incorporate audio-visual material produced for the textbook? (2)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
ii. Does the manual provide teachers with exercises to practice, test, and review vocabulary words? (1,2,3)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
iii. Does the manual provide additional exercises for reinforcing grammar points in the text? (1,2,3)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
III. Context									
A. Is the textbook appropriate for the curriculum? (1,2,19,20)									
i. Does the text coincide with the course goals? (1,2,3,19,20)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
B. Is the textbook appropriate for the students who will be using it? (1,2)									
i. Is the text free of material that might be offensive? (1,6,16)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
ii. Are the examples and explanations understandable? (1)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
iii. Will students enjoy reading the text selections? (1,2,3,15)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
iv. Will the content meet students' felt needs for learning English or can it be adapted for this purpose? (2,3)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	
C. Are the textbook and teacher's manual appropriate for the teacher who will be teaching from them? (1,2,4)									
i. Is the teacher proficient enough in English to use the teacher's manual? (1)	4	3	2	1	0	M	O	N	

42/68

61.7%

Appendix B

Translataion Pages 33-34 from the Spotlight 2 Teacher's Book (Figure 7)

MY LETTERS!

In English, many letter names do not correspond to the sounds they represent. For children, especially at an early age, this makes learning to read challenging since rules do not read many words they encounter early on. This often causes confusion and frustration in learners.

Therefore, in this coursebook, children learn the alphabet by sound, then by letter name. The order is as follows: sound, which represents the letter, and the word with the corresponding sound is pronounced by the teacher, while children see a picture illustrating the word. Then they repeat the sound and the word with the teacher, then from an audio recording and then by themselves. This way, they learn to correlate sound with the graphic form of the letter and recognise the word in context. If a child finds it hard to remember all the letter names (see unit 17), there's no need to insist on learning the whole alphabet right away. They will have the chance to do so throughout the year.

Lesson A (p. 6–7)

Lesson Objectives: Familiarise students with English alphabet letters (a–h) in the correct order, develop the skill of phonetic reading, and teach them to pronounce and recognise the letters correctly.

Reading Vocabulary:

Ant, bed, cat, dog, egg, flag, glass, horse.

Vocabulary/Structure Revision:

Hello! I'm ...

My name is ...

What's your name?

How are you?

That sounds great, thanks.

Goodbye!

Lesson Instructions:

Open your books at page ...!

Listen, point and repeat!

Look and write!

What's this?

Well done, one point, two points.

Visuals for the lesson: My Letters!

Lesson Start

The teacher and students greet each other. The teacher asks: How are you?

Students answer: Fine, thanks.

The teacher invites two students to the board and asks them to introduce themselves.

First, the teacher reminds them how to do it. For example:

Veronika: Hello, I'm Veronika.

Misha: Hello, I'm Misha.

And so on.

Introducing the Alphabet

The teacher writes the letter a on the board and shows a flashcard with the lowercase a.

Shows how it sounds – /æ/.

Students repeat the sound in chorus and individually. The teacher shows a picture of an ant and says: /æ/ — ant.

Then the teacher puts the flashcard next to the letter and attaches a word card, saying the letter and word: a — ant.

Students repeat in chorus and individually.

The teacher then repeats this process for:

a/æ — ant

e/ɛ — egg

i/ɪ — insect

Then, they write the letters on the board and say they will learn to write them.

Students write 1–2 letters in their workbooks (Ex. 4, Unit 1). The rest of the letters and words are introduced in the same way.

The teacher writes in large letters on the board: Open your books to page six.

Exercise 6, Unit 1.

The teacher uses miming and gestures to explain the task and says: Listen, point and repeat!

Students listen to the sounds and words twice in the audio, then repeat them in chorus and individually.

When the recording is played a third time, the teacher shows the letters and words in the textbook.

I want to point out that listening is repeated if needed.

Ex. 6, Unit 1.2

Students listen again, point to the pictures, and look at the letters and words.

During the third playback, they begin to repeat what they've remembered.

Then, the teacher counts how many students pronounced the word correctly and writes the number on the board.

Ex. 7, Unit 1.3

The teacher points to a picture and asks: What's this?

Students answer: horse, cat, etc.

Then, the teacher explains the task and gives time for students to write the names of the words in their notebooks.

To check, the teacher asks the students to name the letter and the word. For example:

h/— horse

a/— ant

g/— glass

d/— dog

e/— egg

f/— flag

b/— bed

End of the Lesson

The class is divided into two teams, A and B.

The teacher draws two columns on the board and labels one A and the other B.

Then shows one of the previously learned letters and asks a student from Team A to name the sound or a word starting with that sound.

If the student answers correctly, the team gets one point.

Students who name both the sound and a word get two points.

The winning team is the one with the most points. For example:

The teacher shows the letter "b."

Team A:

Student: b/ — bed

Teacher: 1 point

Team B:

Student: b/ — bed

Teacher: 1 point

The teacher shows the letter "g."

Team A:

Student: g/ — glass

Teacher: Well done! 2 points

At the end, the teacher says: Goodbye, children!

Students reply: Goodbye (Maria Aleksandrovna)!

Workbook

In class and at home, students complete exercises from the Workbook (Ex. 4, Unit 1, p.2).

Before assigning homework, the teacher explains how to complete it.